

A Study of Farmers Economic Condition in Dharashiv District

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DOI - 10.5281/zenodo.19465660

Abstract:

It is known that farmers are struggling a lot due to their poor financial condition. They work very hard but do not get proper returns. Past records show that the number of farmer suicides is increasing day by day. The main reason for this is that farmers do not earn enough to meet their basic needs. As a result, they take large loans at very high interest rates. When they are unable to repay these loans, some even attempt suicide.

Keyword: Farmers, Economic Fc, Dharashiv District.

Introduction:

Farmers play a very important role in the economic condition of our country. Dharashiv district falls under a drought-prone area, and a large portion of farming depends on rainfall. Therefore, unexpected monsoons directly affect sowing, crop yields, and farmers' income. Unpredictable climate and water scarcity significantly increase the risk of crop failure or low yields, which directly reduces farmers' income. Low market prices further decrease their earnings. Due to insufficient income, farmers are unable to meet their basic needs. As a result, they take large loans, which create a financial burden in the future. This situation has led some farmers to attempt suicide.

Literature Review:

Hebous et al use district-level data on farmer's suicides in two major states during the years 1998 to 2004 to estimate the effects of transitory economic shocks and structural change in agriculture on the incidence of suicides in farm households. To elicit the causal effect of transitory economic shocks on suicides, we use

rainfall conditions as an instrumental variable. For the state of Karnataka, where rainfall and poverty were especially variable around the turn of the millennium, we find that transitory spikes in poverty caused by a lack of rainfall increase suicides among male and decrease suicides among female members of farm households.

In Rajasthan, small and marginal farmers face structural disadvantages that impact their ability to improve farm profitability. According to Chand et al. (2011), the profitability of farms less than two hectares is significantly lower due to limited access to credit, high input costs, and low market prices for produce. These farmers often rely on traditional farming practices, resulting in lower yields compared to large-scale farms that benefit from modern technology and irrigation systems. The average yield per hectare for small farmers in Rajasthan is about 1.8 tonnes, compared to 3.4 tonnes for larger farms (Singh & Ahuja, 2013).

Jagan Kanthi et al Several studies conducted in India have linked the phenomenon of farmer suicides generally to agrarian crisis, particularly to crop failure, raising input prices,

inferior quality of seeds and pesticides, private money lending, inter-linkages of product and credit markets and non-remunerative prices. There is a feeling of insecurity due to crop failure, land alienation and indebtedness. This has resulted in a spate of farmers' suicides in different parts of the country.

Ben whites (1997) in his article, " Agri-industry and contract farmers in the hilly southern region of unpaid west Java", covers two case studies, in both the studies contract farming communities deviate markedly from the neo populist vision of homogeneous, modernizing family farms and differentiation is quite marked and wage labor common. It concludes that institutional framework burdening contract farmers is in serious need of democratization on the problem is not one of formal structure in need of revision but of actual function and subsistence of relationship, which reflect the nature and exercise of power in rural society.

In Spain (Encisco et al., 1995), during the last decade, many farmers have moved from the traditional cereals or horticultural production towards diversification, combining traditional crops with livestock production. Farmers are thus making better use of resources, particularly labour and have often managed to increase their income to the extent that they are able to continue farming and remain in rural areas.

The relationship between income distribution and farm profitability has been widely studied, particularly within the context of developing economies like India. Small and marginal farmers, who constitute most of the agricultural workforce, often experience a disproportionate share of the economic challenges faced in rural areas. Several studies have explored the income disparity in agriculture, showing that farm size, access to resources, and market conditions are crucial determinants of profitability (Narayanamoorthy, 2006).

Research Methodology:

a. Research Design:

For the purpose of this study, a research design has been drafted outlining the steps to be followed in conducting the research systematically. The present research design provides a clear understanding of the process adopted for carrying out this study effectively and in an organized manner.

b. Method Adopted:

This study is based on secondary data. The data were collected from books, research articles, government reports, and reliable websites.

c. Type of Research:

1) Descriptive in nature: As per the nature of study researcher should collect data from books, research articles, government reports, and reliable websites.. For conducting this research, the researcher has used secondary sources of data collection.

Data Analysis:

Our research shows that Dharashiv District is a drought-prone area, and farmers face many difficulties. In this district, the majority of farmers are engaged in marginal and small-scale farming, with land holdings of less than 2 hectares. Due to low rainfall, they often struggle, and sometimes their crops are damaged. As a result, they do not get proper returns, which adversely affects their economic condition.

Interpretation: Here our research study accepted are First hypothesis is Farmers economic condition in Dharashiv District is not good.

In Dharashiv Farmers facing multiple challenges dur to following things:

Financial Condition: Farmers financial conditions are not good because due to drought area they are not getting proper return.

Uncertain Climate: Due to shortage of rainfall farmers fail to Grow, good quality crop. It shows less productivity.

Market Challenges: Due to unexpected rainfall, harvest crop spoil it reduces the quality of product, low quality product gives low return.

Interpretation: In our research, the second hypothesis, which states that farmers face multiple challenges, has been accepted. Due to these challenges, farmers experience several losses. The study shows that farmers face market challenges because their products are often of low quality. As a result, customers are unwilling to pay a good price, and farmers receive very little income, which is insufficient to meet their basic needs. To earn more money, they adopt multiple sources of income.

Interpretation: Here our research study accepted third hypothesis is Farmers are not able to arrange sufficient amount to fulfill their basic needs through farming

Finding:

The research study shows that farmers in Dharashiv district face many problems due to several reasons, including drought, small land holdings, and lack of major river irrigation. These factors result in low-quality crop production. Low-quality crops bring low returns, which adversely affect the economic condition of farmers.

Conclusion:

Finally, I would like to conclude that in Dharashiv district, farming is the primary source of income, but it does not provide adequate returns, which adversely affects the farmers and can also impact the national economy. Some measures need to be taken in favor of farmers, which will definitely help improve their livelihood and standard of living.

References:

1. <http://hdl.handle.net/10603/6834>
2. <http://hdl.handle.net/10603/220233>
3. <http://hdl.handle.net/10603/297937>
4. Ministry of Agriculture. (2016). Pradhan Mantri Fasal Bima Yojana: A comprehensive insurance scheme for farmers. Government of India.
5. Narayanamoorthy, A. (2006). Agricultural credit: A review of the past and a look into the future. *Indian Journal of Agricultural Economics*, 61(4), 688-694.
6. Gill, Anita and Lakhwinder Singh (2006), 'Farmers' Suicides and Response of Public Policy Evidence, Diagnosis and Alternatives from Punjab', *Economic and Political Weekly*, June 30.
7. Mitra, Siddhartha and SangeetaShroff (2007), 'Farmers' Suicides in Maharashtra', *Economic and Political Weekly*, December
8. Jeromi P D (2007), 'Farmers' Indebtedness and Suicides Impact of Agricultural Trade Liberalisation in Kerala', *Economic and Political Weekly*, Aug 4.